

**THE INFLUENCE OF SUPERVISION OF ACADEMIC SUPERVISOR
WITH COMMITMENT AND WORK MOTIVATION ON
PERFORMANCE OF TEACHERS OF THE STATE HIGH SCHOOL
IN BANJARMASIN, INDONESIA**

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Abstract:

The purpose of this research was to describe the influence of supervisor's academic supervision with commitment and motivation of teacher's work behavior at SMAN in Banjarmasin City. The method used was the descriptive method with relational technic. The population in this study as much as 320, the sample based on simple proportional random sampling, which is 178 people. The instrument of data collection is inquiry and questionnaire, which has fulfilled the validity and reliability test using Moment Pearson Product correlation and reliability using Alpha Cronbach were tested to 30 respondents. The results of research hypothesis testing by using SEM AMOS were as follows: (1) there was influence of supervisor's academic supervision on teacher's work commitment, (2) there was influence of supervisor's academic supervision toward teacher's work motivation, (3) there was influence supervisor's supervision to teacher's behavior. (4) there wasn't influence of teacher's commitment to teacher behavior, (5) there was influence of teacher motivation work to teacher behavior, (6) there wasn't indirect influence of supervisor's academic supervision on teacher's behavior through teachers commitment work, and (7) there was indirect influence of supervisor's supervision on teacher behavior through teacher work motivation. Based on the findings of the study; concluded that (1) teachers ask supervisors to supervise, make classroom action research, increase commitment through learning from various book sources, participate in training, motivate themselves to work hard, improve performance compile teaching materials in a continuous manner, (2) the head master works with supervisors to assist teachers in classroom action and research (PTK), provides various science books, (3) the school leader should help teachers to motivate themselves in improving instructional competences.

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1. Introduction

Teacher performance is a very decisive factor for the quality of education and teaching because of its implications for the quality of graduates (output). In RI Law No. 14/2005 part 20 concerning Teachers and Lecturers explains the performance of teachers including as learning planners, implementing teaching and learning activities, and evaluating learning process and the outcomes.

In the era of globalization there is intense competition in the quality aspect in various fields, thus demanding various parties to always improve the area of expertise or competence they have. Therefore, improving the quality of education must be carried out continuously. Even important is to realize development in the character of the nation (nation character building). For that, what needs to be improved from the teacher is the field of competence or expertise (Mulyasa, 2009).

According to Pardede (2013), based on information from the Head of the Middle Education Profession of the Indonesian Ministry of Education and Culture Ambarukmi, low teacher quality can be seen from the average results of the 2013 Teacher Competency Test (UKG) throughout Indonesia, only 42.5. The measurement of UKG results is important, as one to know the competence as a teacher so that it can be measured to what extent teacher competency is.

A conducive school is always oriented towards achieving the vision, mission and goals set and what is needed according to the conditions of the organization. Teachers who have been appointed by the government to teach their knowledge in accordance with the field of expertise. To measure the teaching ability, the teacher at the end of the year has assessed the performance by the principal in a teacher report card called Teacher Performance Assessment (PKG). In PKG it is a necessity that a teacher must achieve a minimum standard of attaining an assessment of the teacher's performance that has been determined that is a minimum of 75.

To realize a quality teacher, the government has been trying to carry out continuous guidance on teachers with various targeted and systematic programs. The coaching program is called academic supervision. Academic supervision as an effort of the education supervisor (supervisor) in helping teachers improve their work patterns and performance, so that it has a positive effect on teaching and learning processes and activities and the quality of education. It is expected to have an impact on improving the quality of learning and improving the quality of schools. A supervisor can play a role in helping the teacher in solving the problems facing the teacher through consultation and discussion, especially the problems in the teaching and learning process according to the scope of the teacher's duties.

Teachers who are able to carry out as educators, instructors and trainers will produce performance, moreover there is an effective influence from the supervisor to

carry out academic supervision, teacher commitment, high work motivation so that the educational goals have been established. Factors that can affect a person's performance are very complex: training, work experience, level of education, personality, personality traits, organization, principal, social attitudes, individual needs, physical condition of the workplace, ability, motivation, and so on (Sutermeister, 1976; Sugiyono, 2007).

Oliva (Muslim, 2008) suggests that not all teachers are skilled in implementing strategies, therefore the supervisor must guide the teacher in the subject, namely: 1) lecture skills, 2) lead discussion skills, and 3) using a variety of activities. Providing academic supervision teaching from the supervisor to the teacher, will help the teacher implement a good teacher's commitment, so that the teacher is enthusiastic and feels compelled or motivated to carry out his duties well.

2. Formulation of The Problem

1. Is there an influence of the supervisor's academic supervision on the high school teacher's commitment in Banjarmasin City?
2. Is there an influence of supervisory supervision on the work motivation of public high school teachers in Banjarmasin City?
3. Is there an influence of supervisor's academic supervision on the performance of public high school teachers in Banjarmasin City?
4. Is there any influence of commitment to the performance of teachers in state high schools in the city of Banjarmasin?
5. Is there any influence of work motivation on the performance of public high school teachers in Banjarmasin City?
6. Is there an indirect influence of supervisory academic supervision through a commitment to the performance of public high school teachers in Banjarmasin City?
7. Is there an indirect influence of supervisory supervision through work motivation on the performance of public high school teachers in Banjarmasin City?

2.1 Research Purposes

1. Describe the influence of the supervisor's academic supervision on the teacher's commitment of public high schools in the city of Banjarmasin.
2. Describe the influence of supervisory supervision on the work motivation of teachers of State High Schools in Banjarmasin City.
3. Describe the influence of the supervisor's academic supervision on the performance of teachers of state high schools in the city of Banjarmasin.
4. Describe the influence of commitment to the performance of teachers in state high schools in the city of Banjarmasin.
5. Describe the influence of work motivation on the performance of teachers in public high schools in the city of Banjarmasin.

6. Describe the indirect influence of supervisory academic supervision through commitment to the teacher performance of state high schools in Banjarmasin City.
7. Describe the indirect influence of supervisory supervision through work motivation on the teacher performance of public high schools in the city of Banjarmasin.

3. Theoretical Basis

A. Academic Supervision of Supervisors

Fathurrohman and Suryana (2011), defining the supervision of teaching (academic) is the role of a supervisor to help solve problems and provide solutions to teachers in improving the ability of teachers through efforts to improve and improve the quality of teaching and learning processes.

According to Sudjana (2006) the principal tasks of supervisory academic supervision are: (1) supervising, (2) advising, (3) monitoring (4) coordinating, and (5) reporting.

B. Work Commitment

According to Spector (2000) work commitment involves an individual's relationship to his work. Work commitment is a variable that reflects the degree of relationship an individual has to a particular job in organizational tasks.

Pugach (2006) describes the related work commitment of teachers, namely: (1) learning from various sources of knowledge, (2) running the curriculum responsibly, (3) discussing the personal needs of students in the classroom and school environment, (4) contributing active in his profession.

3.1 Work Motivation

Maslow's theory; (Sumanto, 2005) work motivation is an urge for humans to do something by working, because in themselves there is enthusiasm or encouragement to meet needs.

According to Herzberg's theory (1959) the teacher's work motivation includes, namely: (1) achievement (successful implementation), (2) recognition (recognition), (3) the work it (work itself), (4) responsibilities (responsibility answer), (5) advancement. Teacher performance is the work ability of a teacher which is seen from the level of achievement, and the completion of the tasks that are his responsibilities in accordance with the requirements that have been set in one field, related to the teaching profession which includes learning planning, implementing teaching and learning assessment of learning outcomes (Rusman, 2009).

The aspect of teacher performance that is measured as an indicator in this study refers to the Teacher's PK which has been developed by the Ministry of National Education based on the State Ministry's Regulation (Permenag) PAN & R No. 16 of 2009, namely: (1) instructional planning, (2) the implementation of active and effective

learning activities: (a) preliminary activities, (b) core activities, (c) closing activities, (3) learning assessment. According to Suriansyah (2015) Ideally, we can classify the teacher as follows: 1. Personal terms 2. Academic requirements, A teacher's academic requirements are a number of knowledge and the skills needed to carry out teaching and educate. Briefly teaching assignments can be grouped into three aspects, namely: a. Planning learning, including academic abilities associated with: 1) Formulate learning objectives 2) Formulating evaluation tools 3) Determine teaching material materials that support achievement aim 4) Formulate learning strategies and determine activities teaching and learning, media and learning resources 5) Carry out formative and summative evaluations b. Carry out learning, including knowledge and the skill of carrying out effective learning processes, which includes: 1) Skill of opening and closing lessons 2) Choosing and organizing teaching materials 3) Skills in choosing and using approaches, models and learning strategies with methods, media and sources right learning. 4) Skills for carrying out classroom management and approaches towards students 5) and o on. c. Conduct and provide guidance to students who are face learning problems. This task is part of the task of the teacher as a mentor as well as mandated by UUGD, in other terms is done by evaluating learning, which includes knowledge and skills in: 1) Select evaluation procedures and techniques 2) Make a good evaluation instrument 3) Evaluate and analyze the results.

4. Methods

This study was designed using descriptive methods with correlational techniques. Correlational techniques, namely research that characterizes the relationship that exists between two or more variables. Correlational research seeks to determine how strong the influence relationship exists between two variables (Arikunto, 2010).

While based on the characteristics of data collection, this type of research uses quantitative research, collecting data in the form of numbers. Data is processed and analyzed to get a scientific information behind these numbers (Sugiyono, 2012).

This study uses the teacher population of public high schools in the city of Banjarmasin. Arikunto (2010: 89) states that what is meant by the population is the overall research subject. In this study, the population is 320 public high school teachers in Banjarmasin City. The sample in this study amounted to 178 teachers from 13 public high schools (SMAN) in Banjarmasin City who were determined using the formula from Slovin.

Research instruments used in collecting data in research using the formula of Slovin tang about the influence of supervisor's academic supervision with the commitment and motivation of the teacher's work on performance is a questionnaire, to retrieve data in writing to the respondents. The grid used in the preparation of instruments in the research here is developed based on the indicators that have been determined from each research variable based on theoretical studies and operational definitions.

The score in this study was determined using a Likert scale which is a more systematic way to give a score on the index (Sugiyono, 2012). In responding to this Likert scale item, respondents were asked to show their preferences by choosing a category rating system that stretched from strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree. Scoring is done by giving the highest score on the very agree and lowest choices for the choice of strongly disagree.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Results

The interpretation of the results of SEM analysis relies on three criteria, namely estimates, critical ratio, and probability. For the purpose of testing hypotheses, the critical ratio criteria are more than 1.96 for the 5% significance level.

In addition to testing hypotheses, the description of the regression equation model is seen through regression coefficients and variable residual intercept values. The following table values the intercept of the residue of each dependent variable.

The design of testing the hypothesis tested in this study is about the presence or absence of a significant influence between the variables under study where the null hypothesis (H_0) is a hypothesis about the absence of influence, which is generally formulated to be rejected while the counterpart hypothesis (H_a) is a hypothesis research.

The hypothesis that will be tested in this study is the extent to which the influence of an independent variable on other dependent variables.

1. Effect of Academic Supervision of Supervisors on Work Commitment of Teachers of State High Schools in Banjarmasin City

SEM structural model analysis shows that there is a positive relationship between academic supervision and work commitment with $\beta = 1.026$ and is significant because $p = 0.000$ or C.R value is $7.952 > 1.96$ at the level of 0.05. Thus, the hypothesis which states that there is no influence of supervisory academic supervision on the work commitment of teachers of State High Schools in Banjarmasin City, is rejected and H_a is accepted.

2. Effect of Academic Supervision of Supervisors on Work Motivation of Teachers of State High Schools in Banjarmasin City

SEM structural model analysis shows that there is a positive correlation of academic supervision with work motivation with $\beta = 0.433$ and is significant because $p = 0.000$ or C.R value of $4.065 > 1.96$ at the level of 0.05. Thus, the hypothesis that there is no influence of supervisory academic supervision on the work motivation of teachers of state high schools in Banjarmasin City, is rejected and H_a is accepted.

3. The Influence of Academic Supervision of Supervisors on the Performance of Teachers of State High Schools in Banjarmasin City

SEM structural model analysis shows that there is a positive relationship between academic supervision and performance with $\beta = 1.303$ and is significant

because $p = 0.044$ or C.R value of $2.014 > 1.96$ at the level of 0.05. Thus, the hypothesis which states that there is no influence of supervisory academic supervision on the teacher performance of public high schools in Banjarmasin City, is rejected and H_a is accepted.

4. Effect of Teacher's Work Commitment on Teacher Performance of State High Schools in Banjarmasin City

SEM structural model analysis shows that there is a negative relationship between teacher's work commitment and performance with $\beta = -0.821$ and is significant because $p = 0.142$ or the value of C.R $-1.96 < -1.467 < 1.96$ at the level of 0.05. Thus, the hypothesis which states that there is no effect of work commitment on the performance of teachers in public high schools in the city of Banjarmasin is accepted. Because there is no influence of work commitment on teacher performance, the regression line equation model cannot be used as a prediction. Means that the results of this study indicate that there is no influence of work commitment on the teacher performance of public high schools in the city of Banjarmasin.

5. Effect of Work Motivation on Teacher Performance in Public High Schools in Banjarmasin City

SEM structural model analysis shows that there is a positive relationship of work motivation with performance with $\beta = 0.119$ and is significant because $p = 0.034$ or the value of C.R is $2.115 > 1.96$ at the level of 0.05. Thus, the hypothesis which states that there is no influence of work motivation on teacher performance in state high schools in Banjarmasin City, is rejected and H_a is accepted.

6. There Is No Indirect Influence of Academic Supervision of Supervisors on the Performance of Teachers of State High Schools in Banjarmasin City

Through Teacher's Work Commitments If the direct relationship coefficient (1.303) is compared with the relationship coefficient value of total supervisor academic supervision and teacher performance (0.4584), there is a significant coefficient difference (< 0.08), then the hypothesis that there is no indirect influence of supervisory academic supervision on the performance of teachers in public high schools in the city of Banjarmasin through teacher work commitment is (H_0) is accepted so that work commitment is an intermediary or intervening variable. The hypothesis is that there is an indirect influence of supervisor's academic supervision on the teacher's performance of public high schools in the city of Banjarmasin through teacher work commitment is rejected. So the results of this study explain that there is no indirect influence of supervisory academic supervision on the performance of teachers of public high schools in the city of Banjarmasin through teacher work commitment even as an intermediary variable.

7. The Indirect Influence of Academic Supervision of Supervisors on the Performance of State High School Teachers in Banjarmasin City

Through Teacher's Work Motivation Direct relationship coefficient (1.303) compared with the relationship coefficient value of total supervisor academic supervision and teacher performance (1.354527), there is no significant coefficient

difference (> 0.08), then the hypothesis stating that there is no indirect influence of supervisory academic supervision on the teacher performance of state high schools in the city of Banjarmasin through the teacher's work motivation is rejected, and H_a is accepted.

5.2 Discussions

The results of this study explain that there is an influence of the supervisor's academic supervision on the work commitment of teachers of State High Schools in Banjarmasin City, according to Sudjana (2006) academic supervision is carried out to improve the quality of teaching-learning guidance processes and student achievement student guidance in order to achieve educational goals. Academic supervision relates to fostering and assisting teachers in improving the quality of the learning guidance process and the quality of student learning outcomes. Through supervisory academic supervision.

The results of this study explain that there is an influence of supervisor's academic supervision on the work motivation of teachers of state high schools in Banjarmasin City, according to Maslow (Sumanto, 2005) humans do something because in themselves there is enthusiasm or encouragement to meet needs. This means that every job done by a person whether consciously or not, is always influenced by the driving force of the need, the drive for that need is called the drive (motive). Motives are forces that encourage someone to act to meet their needs.

The results of this study explain that there is an influence of supervisory academic supervision on the performance of teachers of state high schools in Banjarmasin according to Dewi (2009) the visible performance of teachers who are oriented towards intellectual abilities. The capacity to think immediately is logical, practical and analytical and in accordance with the concept, as well as the concept, as well as the ability to express themselves clearly, firmness.

The results of this study indicate that there is no effect of the teacher's work commitment on the performance of public high school teachers in Banjarmasin City from the opinion of Spector (2000) in general, work commitment involves the individual's relationship to his work. Work commitment is a variable that reflects the degree of relationship that is considered to be owned by an individual towards a particular job in the organization. There is no influence of teacher work commitment on teacher performance, according to Gaffar and Sanusi (2002) teachers have had duties in the field of education because they already have an obligation in the implementation of teaching tasks, planning teaching materials, learning process, make a structured task, interact with the teacher and students, evaluate learning outcomes, mastery of material and research methodology at school.

The results of this study indicate that there is an effect of the teacher's work motivation on the performance of public high school teachers in the city of Banjarmasin according to Mc Clelland (1976) states that work motivation is not something that can be inherited, due to the influence of the situation around it, then work motivation can

be formed following the individual's way of need high for achievement prefers work situations with personal responsibility, feedback, and a risk with intermediate degrees.

The results of this study indicate that there is no indirect influence of supervisory academic supervision on the performance of public high school teachers in the city of Banjarmasin through work commitment, according to Arikunto (2008) the purpose of supervision supports the creation of an optimal work atmosphere, especially in the quality of learning conducted by teachers who indicated by the success of graduates. Sallis (1994) explains that the teaching performance of teachers is inseparable from the quality (quality) of the teacher as a "slippery concept" concept. Through the work commitment of Arikunto (2004), it can be seen from a person's willingness to be actively involved in an activity with high responsibility, not just mere involvement. While the teaching performance of teachers is inseparable from the discussion of the quality of the teacher itself. Quality is a term related to the point of view and the angle of work interest.

The results of this study explain that there is an indirect influence of supervisory academic supervision on the performance of public high school teachers in the city of Banjarmasin through work motivation, Arikunto (2008) argued that the objectives of supervision include: supporting the creation of an optimal work atmosphere, in which students can achieve learning outcomes as expected. Sanusi (2002) describes individuals who have performance, namely (a) constructive actions, (b) believe in themselves, (c) be responsible, (d) have a love for work, (e) have a foresight, (f) able to overcome problems and adapt to a changing environment, (g) contribute and be innovative, (h) have the power to realize its potential, and (i) have the ability: such as skills, knowledge, qualifications, experience and characteristics. According to Maslow; (Sumanto, 2005) humans do something because in themselves there is enthusiasm or encouragement to meet needs.

6. Conclusion and Recommendation

6.1 Conclusion

The results of this study concluded: (1) there was an influence of supervisor's academic supervision on teacher's work commitment, (2) there was an influence of supervisor's academic supervision on teacher's work motivation, (3) there was influence of supervisor's academic supervision on teacher's performance, (4) there was no influence of commitment teacher work on teacher performance, (5) there is an effect of teacher work motivation on teacher performance, (6) there is no indirect influence of supervisor academic supervision on teacher performance through teacher work commitment, and (7) there is an indirect influence of supervisory academic supervision on performance teacher through teacher work motivation.

6.2 Recommendation

The results of this study are suggested: (1) teachers ask supervisors to supervise, make classroom action research, increase commitment through learning from various book sources, participate in training, motivate themselves to work hard, improve performance compile teaching materials in a continuous manner, (2) the head master works with supervisors to assist teachers in classroom action and research (PTK), provides various science books, improves teacher work motivation, guides teachers to improve performance, (3) supervisors are advised to nurture teachers, activate MGMP, (4) the head of the Department of Education and Culture of the Province of South Kalimantan is advised to carry out curriculum training, classroom action research to teachers, involving supervisors to improve academic supervision.

References

- Arikunto, S. 2004. *Manajemen Pengajaran Secara Manusiawi*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Arikunto, S. 2008. *Dasar-Dasar Supervisi*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Arikunto, S. 2010. *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktek*. Jakarta: PT. Rineka Cipta.
- Dewi, I., S. 2009. *Integrasi Teknologi Komunikasi*. Yogyakarta: Amara Book.
- Fathurrohman and Suryana. 2011. *Profesi Keguruan*. Jakarta: Diadit Media.
- Gaffar and Sanusi. 2002. *Perencanaan Pendidikan: Teori dan Metodologi*. Jakarta: Proyek PLPTK Dirjen Dikti Depdikbud.Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Herzberg, F. 1959. *One More Time: How Do You Motivate Employees*. New York: Harvard Business Review.
- McClelland, D., C., et al. 1976. *The Achievement Motive*. New York: Appleton Century Craffs Inc.
- Mulyasa, E. 2009. *Standar Kompetensi dan Sertifikasi Guru*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Muslim, S.B. 2008. *Supervisi Pendidikan Meningkatkan Kualitas Profesionalisme Guru*. Mataram: Alfabeta.
- Pardede. 2013. *Hasil Uji Etos kerja (UKG) 2013*. [Http://www.id.com](http://www.id.com). Diakses 12 Februari 2014.
- Permeneg PAN and RB No 16 Tahun 2009 tentang Penilaian Kinerja Guru. Jakarta: Kementerian Pendayagunaan Aparatur Negara.
- Pugach, M. C. 2006. *Because Teaching Matters*. USA: Willey/Jossey-Bass Education.
- Rusman. 2009. *Penilaian Kinerja Guru*. Jakarta: PT. RajaGrafindo Persada.
- Suriansyah, A., Aslamiah., Sulisyana. 2015. *Perspektif Guru Profesional*. Jakarta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada
- Sallis, E. 1994. *Total Quality Management in Education*. London: Kogan Page Educational Management Series.

- Sanusi, A. 2002. *Kapita Selekta Pembahasan Masalah Sosial dan Pendidikan*. Bandung: FPS IKIP Bandung.
- Spector. 2000. *Decision Making*. Online. <http://www//wikipedia.org.wiki>. Diakses 21 September 2017.
- Sudjana, N. 2006. *Manajemen Program Pendidikan: Untuk Pendidikan Nonformal dan Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia*. Bandung: Penerbit Faith Production.
- Sugiyono, W, E., 2007. *Statistika Penelitian dan Aplikasinya Dengan SPSS 20 for Windows*. Bandung: CV. Albeta.
- Sugiyono. 2012. *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif Kuantitatif dan R & D*. Alfabet. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Sumanto. 2005. *Kepemimpinan Pendidikan*. Jakarta: PT. Bina Aksara.
- Undang-Undang RI Nomor 14 Tahun 2005 tentang Guru dan Dosen. Jakarta: Departemen Pendidikan Nasional.

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